

Skills 4 eosc

D5.1 FAIR and RDM training modules for RI professionals

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable presents the Course on Data Management for Research Infrastructure (RI) professionals developed as part of Task T5.1 of the Skills4EOSC project, in collaboration with the RItrainPlus project. It outlines the learning objectives, the structure of the course modules, and the content of the training materials. The training targets are managers, operators and other professionals supporting the services provided by Research Infrastructures or Core Facilities, as well as prospective trainers in this field.

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	<i>Name</i>	<i>Partner/Activity</i>	<i>Date</i>
<i>From:</i>	Marialuisa Lavitrano	UNIMIB	05/2025
<i>Moderated by:</i>			
<i>Reviewed by:</i>	Arnaud Gingold Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou	AMU OPERAS	06/2025
<i>Approved by:</i>	Sara Di Giorgio Claudio Prandoni	GARR	06/2025

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

<i>Terminology/Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>
CC	Competence Centre(s)
CPD	Continuing Professional Development
CF	Core Facilities
EQF	European Qualification Framework
ESMRI	European School for Management of Research Infrastructures
MVS	Minimum Viable Skillset
OS	Open Science
RDM	Research Data Management
RI	Research Infrastructure
TtT	Train-the-Trainer

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Executive Summary

This deliverable outlines a training framework for Research Infrastructure (RI) professionals, and introduces the skills and competencies required to support the research communities in engaging with RIs and implementing digital research workflows.

The deliverable is the main output of T5.1 "OS and RDM skills for Research Infrastructures professionals", which addresses current and emerging Open Science (OS) and FAIR Research Data Management (RDM) practices, with an aim to upskill RI professionals in OS-related aspects. The primary objective of the course is to establish a framework for the standardisation of best practices in data management and data policy within RIs; thus, it serves as a preparatory step for the Skills4EOSC Train-the-Trainer (TtT) activities.

The pilot course was delivered in September 2024 and was attended by 30 participants. It was designed as a Continuing Professional Development (CPD) programme at post-8 level of the European Qualification Framework (EQF), with the general aim of developing Knowledge, Skills, and Competence for professionals already employed in RIs and Core Facilities (CFs).

The learning model, teaching tools, and methodologies included online modules, lectures, group work, case discussions, role plays, sharing best practices, and assignments. Faculty members from RIs contributed to module design and provided problems, case studies, and scenarios for developing rich active learning materials. The delivery of the pilot course was followed by a thorough assessment and fine-tuning of the learning modules.

The report of the pilot course can be accessed at <https://zenodo.org/records/14710934>.

1 Introduction

Data is a valuable asset in RIs, serving as the foundation for scientific discoveries, innovation, and policy development. Effective data management is a cornerstone for the successful operation of Research Infrastructures (RIs). Proper data management ensures that research outputs are reproducible, credible, and reusable, leading to more efficient collaborations and higher research impact.

As data continues to grow in volume, complexity, and importance, RI managers and operators must adopt robust data management strategies to ensure data accessibility, interoperability, security, and long-term preservation. The suggested learning path covers a wide range of topics such as: the role of data policy; data typologies; metadata; data lifecycle; open data; and data sharing. Accordingly, the training modules presented provide a comprehensive overview of the key issues and concepts around the management of data and data policy in RIs and Core Facilities. The conceptual design of the modules addresses key considerations for managers, emerging workflows, best practices and mechanisms, with a special focus on OS and FAIR principles as an integral part of RI operation.

The modules were created in collaboration with the RItrainPlus project,¹ which focuses on establishing the European School for Management of Research Infrastructures (ESMRI). Upon completion of the learning path, participants are expected to be able to (a) develop relevant data management policies and guidelines, and (b) determine resources, technologies, and staff competencies needed to implement data management and policy, as well as FAIR principles in their RI.

As part of the Task’s activities, a training pilot was delivered in September 2024 with an aim to assess the relevance and currency of the learning path. The pilot was designed as a Continuing Professional Development (CPD) programme at post-8 level of the European Qualification Framework (EQF), with the general aim of developing Knowledge, Skills, and Competence for professionals already employed in RIs and Core Facilities (CFs).

¹ <https://ritrainplus.eu/>

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The learning model, teaching tools, and methodologies included online modules, lectures, group work, case discussions, role plays, sharing best practices, and assignments. Faculty members from RIs contributed to module design and contributed with exercises, case studies, and scenarios for developing rich active learning materials. Slides were used as the main support for instruction. For many of the exercises there were “break-out rooms” in smaller groups. Also, collaborative tools such as Mentimeter and Google Jamboard were used to enhance the learning experience .

The pilot course was attended by 30 participants, and was followed by a thorough assessment and fine-tuning of the learning modules through a survey.

2 Learning Path

2.1 Methodology

The design of the training followed a competency-based methodology, aimed at addressing the specific needs of professionals working within RIs and Core Facilities (CF). Its content is relevant and adaptable to the evolving practices of RI governance, operations, and service provision.

2.1.1 Definition of Learning Path

The course is intended as a learning path for RI and CF managers, operators and other professionals, as well as prospective trainers in the field. It is structured as a collection of progressive thematic modules, beginning with fundamental concepts and continuing towards applied, operational competencies. Each module maps to the relevant Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS), and to specific phases of RI service development, ensuring practical alignment with their operational framework, and the role of the targeted professional profiles. The resources described in this report are designed to provide new trainers with FAIR-by-Design reusable and customisable training materials. The methodologies of the Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) and FAIR-by-Design developed within the Skills4EOSC project have been applied to ensure that training modules are tailored to the specific needs of RI professionals.

The following themes guided the designing of the learning path:

1. Understand the key issues and concepts around the management of data and data policy within an operational RI.
2. Situate the RI within a typology of research infrastructures and appreciate how this influences the treatment of data management and policy.
3. Assess the different factors at play when implementing data management and policy in real-time settings, such as resources, technologies, and staff competencies.
4. Recognise FAIR principles and practices in the context of RI and CF.
5. Apply the methodologies of the Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) and FAIR-by-Design developed within the Skills4EOSC project to ensure that training modules are tailored to the specific needs of RI professionals.

2.1.2 Modules

The learning path has been developed around 4 modules:

- Module 1 - Introduction to data management and data policy for RI managers: introduces the key concepts of RDM and the role of data policy. It introduces the role of RI managers within the OS landscape.
- Module 2 - Data Policy in Research Infrastructure Systems: explores the operational dimensions of data policies within RIs. It focuses on compliance with standards, and stakeholder engagement as targeted policy audiences.
- Module 3 - FAIR principles and their application: outlines practical strategies and tools to operationalise FAIR in RI services and workflows.
- Module 4 - Data Management Plan for Research Infrastructures: focuses on the development, evaluation, and implementation of Data Management Plans (DMP). It links DMPs to planning, service provision, and long-term data curation.

2.2 Training Materials

The training materials are largely based on existing materials by experts from Research Infrastructures and Research Performing Organizations partners of RItrainPlus project, repurposed to adhere to the scope of this learning path.

They are composed of:

- A learning plan (described in this document)
- Slides, available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15763772> (Module 1), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15763779> (Module 2), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15763801> (Module 3), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15763813> (Module 4)
- Slides Guidelines for trainers_MVS_Leaning Outcomes, available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15763753>
- Data management for RI professional_MVS, available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15763738>

All materials are provided on editable supports (e.g. PPT slides) and complete with licensing information, as well as with a plan of the learning path and notes and indications for Training facilitators.

3 Modules & Learning Objectives

3.1 Module 1 - Introduction to data management and data policy for RI managers

Title	Introduction to data management and data policy for RI managers
Abstract / Description	Module 1 provides a framework for the course and presents the key concepts relevant to managing data and data policy within RIs, including definitions of data and typologies of RIs, the role of metadata, and operational considerations for managers.
Author(s)	UNIMIB
Primary Language	English
Keyword(s)	Data Management, Data Policy, Research Infrastructures (RIs), Metadata, Data Governance
*Version Date	v1 03/2025
URL to Resource	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15763772
Resource URL Type	DOI
License	CC by international 4.0
Access Cost	NO
Target Group (Audience)	RI and CF Managers and Operators
Learning Resource Type	Presentation (PPTX)
Learning Outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Understanding the key issues and concepts around the management of data and data policy within an operational RI; ▪ Situate RIs within a typology of research infrastructures, and appreciate how this influences the treatment of data management and policy;

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Determining how different drivers affect how data management and data policy are implemented in an RI; ▪ Assessing the different relevant factors in play when implementing data management and policy in real-time settings, such as resources, technologies, and staff competencies.
Expertise (Skill) Level	Beginner, Intermediate

3.2 Module 2 - Data Policy in Research Infrastructure Systems

Title	Data Policy in Research Infrastructure Systems
Abstract / Description	Module 2 covers the role of data policy and data management in RIs, including how data policy for different data management domains should be crafted and formulated for different audiences and purposes, and aligned with internal and external drivers and implemented in RI workflows. It also addresses how policy can be converted into practical guidelines for different user groups.
Author(s)	UNIMIB
Primary Language	English
Keyword(s)	Data Policy, Research Infrastructures (RIs), Data Management, Policy Implementation, Stakeholder Alignment
*Version Date	v1 03/2025
URL to Resource	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15763779
Resource URL Type	DOI
License	CC by international 4.0
Access Cost	NO
Target Group (Audience)	RI and CF Managers and Operators

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Learning Resource Type	Presentation (PPTX)
Learning Outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ identifying and developing relevant data management policies for RIs throughout the data lifecycle; ▪ defining appropriate workflows, roles, and responsibilities among research infrastructure staff for data management and policy implementation; ▪ understanding, cataloguing, and managing different types of data (datasets, software, workflows, etc.) handled and generated in the RI and by its users; ▪ deciding what is needed to make data and metadata accessible for long-term preservation; ▪ understanding data sharing and access (open data vs closed data) and restrictions/control in an OS context; and assessing certification mechanisms available for data management in different research infrastructures/scientific communities and determine whether they are needed for the research infrastructure
Expertise (Skill) Level	Beginner, Intermediate

3.3 Module 3 - FAIR principles and their application

Title	FAIR principles and their application
Abstract / Description	Module 3 focuses on deepening the participants' understanding of the FAIR principles and empowering them to adapt and extend the principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability in their RI. By the end of this Module, participants will be able to set up the guidelines for FAIRness in their Research

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	Infrastructure, and plan the development and/or integration of the protocols, techniques and tools required to achieve such FAIRness.
Author(s)	UNIMIB
Primary Language	English
Keyword(s)	FAIR Principles, Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability
*Version Date	v1 03/2025
URL to Resource	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15763801
Resource URL Type	DOI
License	CC by international 4.0
Access Cost	NO
Target Group (Audience)	RI and CF Managers and Operators
Learning Resource Type	Presentation (PPTX)
Learning Outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ understanding the FAIR principles in general and the main concepts and vocabulary used; ▪ making data findable, understanding the most common metadata schemas and the importance of generating persistent identifiers; ▪ making data accessible, describing the different protocols to access data, both for humans and for machines; ▪ making data interoperable, using ontologies and other semantic artifacts; ▪ making data reusable, selecting the appropriate license and providing rich metadata to facilitate its reuse and provenance; ▪ implementing FAIR principles in the setting of a real RI.
Expertise (Skill) Level	Beginner, Intermediate

3.4 Module 4 - Data management plan for Research Infrastructures

Title	Data management plan for Research Infrastructures
Abstract / Description	Module 4 turns the theoretical knowledge of data management policies and plans into practice. Developing a reliable and specific data management plan is a core business of each research infrastructure. A data management plan ensures that the RI's data will be adequately described and made available to a broader public. This enables a more thorough perspective for the re-use of data and the formulation of innovative data-centric research questions.
Author(s)	UNIMIB
Primary Language	English
Keyword(s)	Data Management Plan (DMP), Research Infrastructures (RIs), Data Reuse, Data Documentation, Open Data
*Version Date	v1 03/2025
URL to Resource	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15763813
Resource URL Type	DOI
License	CC by international 4.0
Access Cost	NO
Target Group (Audience)	RI and CF Managers and Operators
Learning Resource Type	Presentation (PPTX)

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Learning Outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ understanding the importance of dedicated data management plans for increased data quality of the RI's main assets; ▪ supporting compliance with the RI's data management policies; ▪ contributing to knowledge exchange with regard to data management by the RI's gateway function; ▪ increasing the quality of service in their RI by improving the essential cornerstones of research data management plans; ▪ developing an individual and personalised template for a data management plan for the participants' RI; ▪ ensuring improved quality of the draft template by expert-level feedback after assessment of the provided data management plan template.
Expertise (Skill) Level	Beginner, Intermediate

3.5 Learning Objectives

Topic	Learning Objective
Data management policies	Identify and develop relevant data management policies for research infrastructures, throughout the data lifecycle.
Data management policies	Define appropriate workflows, roles, and responsibilities among RI staff for data management.
Data management policies	Understand, catalogue and manage different types of data (understood in a broad sense: datasets, software, workflows, etc.) that are handled and generated in the RI and by RI users.
Data management policies	Setup the data management plan policies and

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	ensure that RI staff and researchers develop data management plans according to these policies.
Data management policies	Learn the certification mechanisms that are available for data management in different RIs/scientific communities, and be able to determine whether these are needed for your RI.
FAIR principles	Identify the FAIR principles that are applicable for the data generated by the Research Infrastructure.
FAIR principles	How to manage metadata within your RI system (F of FAIR plus other elements of FAIR).
FAIR principles	Make the data of the RI more interoperable (I of FAIR).
FAIR principles	Make your data more findable and citeable (F of FAIR).
FAIR principles	Ensure that data can be used and reused as much as possible (R or F of FAIR).
Security and privacy	Learn about the importance of data security and how to spot potential gaps within the infrastructure and internal processes.
Security and privacy	Learn about the importance of data privacy/protection policies and techniques and how to apply them.
Security and privacy	Data sharing and access (open data vs closed data) and restrictions/control, in an Open Science context.
Security and privacy	Learn about the importance of data security and how to spot potential gaps within the infrastructure and internal processes.
Security and privacy	Learn about the importance of data privacy/protection policies and techniques and how to apply them.
Preservation	Learn what is needed to make data and metadata accessible for the long-term (preservation).
Data management plans	Understand the importance of dedicated data management plans for increased data quality of the Research Infrastructures main assets.

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Data management plans	Support compliance with Research Infrastructures' data management policies.
Data management plans	Contribute to knowledge exchange with regard to data management by Research Infrastructures' gateway function.
Data management plans	Focus on the essential cornerstones of research data management plans for increased quality of service provisioning.
Data management plans	Understand, catalogue and manage different types of data (understood in a broad sense: datasets, software, workflows, etc.).
Data management plans	Templating mechanisms for Data Management Plans.
Data management plans	Understand the different requirements for data and metadata descriptions related to different data types of various Research Infrastructures.
Data management plans	Develop an individual and personalised template for a data management plan for the Research Infrastructures.
Data management plans	Ensure improved quality of the draft template by expert level feedback after assessment of the provided data management plan template.
Skills4EOSC methodologies	Apply the methodologies of the Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) and FAIR-by-Design developed within the Skills4EOSC project to ensure that training modules are tailored to the specific needs of RI professionals.

4 Pilot

4.1 Pilot Delivery

A pilot training was run in September 2024 to assess the learning path and collect feedback from participants.

The pilot was structured as a Continuing Professional Development (CPD) programme aligned with Level 8 of the European Qualifications Framework (EQF). It employed a blended learning approach, incorporating online modules, case discussions, best practice sharing, and assignments.

The report of the pilot course can be accessed at <https://zenodo.org/records/14710934>.

4.2 Pilot Outcomes

The Course was aimed at managers, operators and other professionals in research infrastructures or core facilities. It was attended by 30 participants - professionals working in research infrastructures or core facilities, at different career stages. All 30 participants completed the training and provided feedback.

Feedback and assessment were conducted through a designed survey. Participants were invited to complete a questionnaire, and provided specific feedback on individual modules, following either an online questionnaire or comments made in debriefing sessions after modules.

Overall, participants expressed appreciation for hands-on exercises and real-world examples in addition to theoretical content. Future trainers should strive to strike a balance between theory and practical application to enhance engagement and comprehension.

5. Discussion – Next Steps

Feedback from participants has been instrumental in refining the Course. Participants provided detailed insights into their experiences with individual modules, highlighting areas of strength and suggesting targeted improvements.

For instance, while the introductory module received praise for its comprehensive coverage, some participants expressed a desire for more advanced content to supplement the foundational material. In response, the final version of the Course incorporates additional advanced topics to cater to a broader range of participant expertise.

Similarly, the module on data policy elicited mixed feedback, with some participants finding the content clear and informative, while others felt overwhelmed by the amount of information presented. Fine-tuning the balance between depth and accessibility has been a focus for the final edition of the Course, ensuring that all participants can engage meaningfully with the material. In the “FAIR principles” module, participants appreciated the initial level of instruction but found the later segments to be overly complex. Adjusting the pacing and structure of this module to ensure a smooth progression of concepts has been a priority for the final edition.

The module on data management plans, while comprehensive, was noted for its extensive content. Breaking down this module into smaller, more focused sessions improved comprehension and retention among participants.

Looking ahead, several avenues for enhancement and expansion were considered to further improve the Course and maximise its impact on RI managers.

1. Proactive measures have been implemented to better gauge participant backgrounds and experience levels before the start of the course. This may involve administering pre-course surveys or conducting introductory assessments to tailor the content to the specific needs of participants.
2. Maintaining a balance between online and in-person interaction is another area of focus. While the online format offers accessibility, face-to-face interactions can enhance the learning experience and foster deeper engagement. Exploring hybrid approaches that combine online theory sessions with in-person exercises may provide the best of both worlds.

6. Reusing the Learning Path and Training materials

Trainers are welcome to reuse the developed materials which can be replicated.

Resource bundles are provided with Readme, Licence and Machine-readable citation files to help you providing proper attribution for the source materials.

For any questions related to the materials, their version, and/or training on the management of RIs, as well as any feedback and suggestions to improve the materials, contact [marialuisa.lavitran\[at\]unimib.it](mailto:marialuisa.lavitran[at]unimib.it).

7 References

Ritrain plus [n.d.] <https://ritrainplus.eu/> . Last Accessed 25 June 2025.

Annex: Links to relevant resources and documentation

- ENVRI-FAIR D4.6 Draft policy document for common service catalogue
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